

Community Archives and Heritage Group Conference 2024

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In this blog, Nella McNicol from the OHOS Archives Lab at the University of Glasgow discusses her time at the Community Archives and Heritage Group's 2024 conference.

On Wednesday, 10th July 2024, the [Community Archives and Heritage Group](#) (CAHG) hosted its annual [Conference](#) at University College London. It brought together various speakers from local authority archives, community archives and related community heritage groups across the country, reaching the most northern parts of the rural Scottish Highlands down to the bustling host city of London. This year's theme, 'Community Archives, Keeping Community at the Heart of Archives and Heritage', can be viewed not only as a title but perhaps a call to action. Through our exploration of the role communities have in creating archival materials and the steps that must be taken to preserve these, this theme strongly aligns with the Our Heritage, Our Stories ethos.

The conference showcased numerous community-based archival initiatives and projects. It was heartening to note that both speakers and organisers frequently referred to *Our Heritage, Our Stories*, emphasising the positive impact the project has had on the sector since its launch a few years ago.

The discussions delved into the intricate and sometimes daunting nature of preserving digital content, focusing on collaboration as crucial when safeguarding our digital heritage. Karyn Williamson from the [Digital Preservation Coalition](#), who we have been thrilled to have on the OHOS team since March this year, focused on this topic during her keynote address. Karyn outlined the steady changes that have been occurring in the sector's relationship with both community content and digital materials over several decades. Now, separation between community and mainstream archives is not viable, and a change in mindset is required for

collaboration to become the norm. Karyn highlighted the contribution the OHOS project has made to changing this mindset by demonstrating that consistent support when preserving community content is possible and extremely worthwhile. However, striking the balance between supporting community archives while also encouraging their independence is one of the many challenges and complexities involved in forming effective and worthwhile collaboration.

Stevan Lockhart from [Assynt Community Digital Archive](#) explored digital preservation of community-generated digital content while Sean Rippington, Digital Archivist and Copyright Manager at [St Andrew's University](#), discussed methods that mainstream archives could use to connect with community archives. Sean noticed barriers when it came to terms being used, and guidance was required to cover different access points. Sean felt it would be better to help community archives by doing this on their own terms. He noted that the workshops run with OHOS were sometimes tricky to deliver because the participants' needs and expectations ranged so widely. In fact, the issue of covering topics relevant to all the different community archives was illustrated in some Q&A sections during the conference. For example, in response to Karyn's talk, an audience member sought practical guidance for formatting emails correctly to preserve them in their archive. Evidently, the reasons for some community groups to attend these events will contrast with archivists or even other community archives depending on their own unique and varied experiences, problems, and priorities.

Overall, gaining different perspectives from trained archivists and members of community heritage groups was invaluable, proving the efficacy of collaborative discussions and the urgent need for unification across the sector. Both community and established archives must come together in a way that allows community archives to receive support on their own terms. This approach empowers the communities while creating a solid community within the archive sector itself.

A final reflection from CAHG chairperson, Jane Golding, summarised the conference perfectly:

A deeper appreciation for the fragility of records is required for the important digital content created by communities to be preserved long-term. Only then can we effectively keep community archives at the heart of the community.

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